

Conservation of Momentum in terms of Probability, Space and Time Part III

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In Parts I and II, we argued that the $\exp(ipx)$ free particle wavefunction form of quantum mechanics is really a mathematical probability type function which ensures conservation of momentum, but can only do so by involving two variables, x, p , such that one has orthogonal functions in x for p_1 and p_2 . In other words, an averaging is done in space through $\exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ and if one has crests canceling troughs, then on average one does not have a p_1 to p_2 transition for p_1 and p_2 being different.

This suggests that if one creates linear combinations of $\exp(ipx)$ s in the form of a complex function $W(x)$ such that $W^*(x)W(x)$ forms a constant in x space, then such a scenario does not violate conservation of momentum. This can be generalized to $W^* (-i\hbar/dx) W$ which yields an average momentum flow. For $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$, one has momentum flow in that space. In fact, if one considers the coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$ to represent square root flux, then $A\exp(-ipx) A (-i\hbar/dx) \exp(ipx) = p A^2$, i.e. average pressure. For equilibrium or steady state situations, one may expect an average constant pressure. In keeping with this idea, we examine a function $J(x) = W^* (-i\hbar/dx) W + (i\hbar/dx) W dW/dx$ introduced in (1) and used for asymptotic scattering wavefunction pieces. We interpret this as average momentum flux and apply it to the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem. In order for $J(x)$ or $\langle p \text{ density} \rangle = \text{constant}$, one requires that $d/dx d/dx W_{\text{real}} = \text{constant } W_{\text{real}}$ and $d/dx d/dx W_{\text{imaginary}} = \text{same constant } W_{\text{imaginary}}$. If one considers the function to be linked to pressure and p , then $\text{constant} = p$ and $\exp(ipx) = W$ for a single p . One may, however, create other W functions which have a single p , but are a mixture of incident and reflected fluxes.

The basic idea which we wish to present is that the math function/probability $\exp(ipx)$ used to ensure conservation of momentum (if one integrates over x) also serves to define momentum density $\exp(-ipx) (-i\hbar/dx) \exp(ipx)$. If this is constant and the coefficient of $\exp(ipx)$ is square root flux, one may use the continuity of the p and x variables (two equations) to ultimately establish pressure equilibrium (on average). Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ becomes a useful function, not only ensuring conservation of momentum, but defining average pressure which may be used to solve problems which cannot be solved using Newtonian mechanics, i.e. one dimensional reflection-refraction.

$\exp(ipx)$ and Conservation of Momentum

In Parts I and II, $\exp(ipx)$ was introduced as a special math function which ensures conservation of momentum if one integrates over x and uses $\exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x)$ to test if one can jump from p_2 to p_1 . Here we suggest that in the case of $p_1 = p_2 = p$ one has 1. This is useful because if one inserts $(-i\hbar/dx)$ one has a momentum density function. If this is constant, then one has momentum flux (i.e. pressure if the coefficient of $\exp(ipx)$ is taken to be square root flux). This flux is consistent with momentum conservation. The reason that average pressure is useful is that one may consider an equilibrium picture (in some cases) as having the same pressure in different x places.

To see this in more detail, we consider a function introduced in (1) for scattering.

Function $J(x)$ such that $dJ/dx=0$

In (1), scattering from a potential is considered and current function $J(x)$ is defined:

$$J(x) = W^*(x) (-id/dx) W(x) + W(x) (id/dx) W^*(x) \quad ((1))$$

Here we do two things, First, we ask: Why should one consider a function such as ((1)) and secondly, we ask what restrictions does $dJ/dx=0$ impose on W ? If one wishes to have dJ/dx , the simplest solution is $J=\text{constant}$. If one instead wishes to introduce a math function which depends on x , then given that one takes d/dx of the overall function, one might expect $W dW/dx$ to appear together with a minus term. This cannot occur for W real, but it can for W complex, i.e. ((1)).

From the point of view of $\exp(ipx)$, we note that $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is kind of average pressure if $a(p)$'s are square root of flux values. Without using $\exp(ipx)$, one may ask: What is the condition for $dJ/dx=0$?

$$d/dx \text{ } d/dx W_{\text{real}} = C W_{\text{real}} \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dx \text{ } d/dx W_{\text{imaginary}} = C W_{\text{imaginary}} \quad ((2b))$$

This leads to $\exp(iC x)$ as a solution, but it is not clear what C is. One may see that such a solution leads to $\exp(-i C_1 x) \exp(i C_2 x)$, integrated over x (i.e. averaged in a sense) equalling 0 if $C_1 \neq C_2$. Thus, C_1 seems to be linked to a conserved quantity. We suggest that the fundamental conserved quantity from Newtonian mechanics is momentum p . Thus, one may suggest $\exp(ipx)$ as being a solution of ((2)). It is, however, not the only solution. One could have $A \exp(ipx) - B \exp(-ipx)$ and obtain a $J(x)$ proportional to p , but with a more complicated coefficient.

We try to apply these ideas to one dimensional reflection-refraction.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

Consider a single photon which either reflects or refracts. First, unlike fluid mechanics (large to small pipe) not all of the particles move from one x region to the next due to reflection, so one does not consider flux conservation at $x=0$, the n_1-n_2 junction, where n is the index of refraction. Secondly, even though

$$1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract}) \quad ((3))$$

one really considers an average in time. For instance, if one only examined a single photon, it either reflects or refracts and so one would only be aware of one possible outcome. Furthermore, due to probability, the first three photons might all reflect, so the idea of a time average is important. This time average, however, becomes associated with three fluxes, AA , BB , CC for the incident, reflected and refracted photons. Flux is not conserved and even though reflection and refraction occur when the incident photon has disappeared, the average over time

(flux picture) involves incident, reflected and refracted beams at the same time. If one wishes to have conservation of pressure classically, then:

$$AA p - BBp = CC p^2 \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is an average pressure equation which represents a kind of equilibrium. If A is known, B and C represent two unknowns and so one might consider the problem unsolvable.

The unusual probability $\exp(ipx)$, however, is used to show conservation of momentum in space. If $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx)$ is a constant, then momentum is conserved i.e. one part $\exp(ipx)$ represents a possible flow. If $W^* W$ has crests and troughs which cancel, then this is not a flow which happens. This idea of acceptable p flows should be applicable to the one dimensional -reflection refraction case. If p and $-p$ represent the reflected rays and p_2 the refracted, one may have flows on either side of x_0 .

If one examines $J(x)$, one may see that it may be constructed from:

$$W_{\text{left side}}(x_0) = W_{\text{right side}}(x) \quad ((5a))$$

$$\text{and } d/dx W_{\text{left side}}(x) = d/dx W_{\text{right side}}(x) \quad ((5b))$$

Thus, even though flux is not conserved, a probability linked with momentum conservation is. Writing: $W_{\text{left side}} = A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx)$ and $W_{\text{right side}} = C \exp(ip_2 x)$

One sees that it is average momentum in terms of flux which is conserved at x_0 by combining (multiplying) ((5a)) by ((5b)) and evaluating at $x_0=0$ or using $J(x)$.

Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is not only used to show conservation of momentum through integrating over dx $\exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ipx)$, but also may be used to construct average pressures which do not average out. This average pressure, however, really a combination of two continuity equations, using p and x , from $\exp(ipx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Parts I and II we argued that $\exp(ipx)$ is a special math probability which ensures conservation of momentum over space (x). This is based on the idea that if equally sized crests and troughs are present in $\exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$, they cancel. In other words, one may create functions $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and consider $W^*(x)W(x)$ and even $W^* d/dx W$ to see if there is momentum flow which does not average out.

For $\exp(ipx)$ or even $A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx)$, this momentum flow is constant and so does not average out. The point we make is that $\exp(ipx)$ is a function of x and p and one may create two continuity equations in order to create the conserved momentum flux $W^* (id/dx) W + W (-id/dx) W^*$, namely $W(x_0)_{\text{left}} = W(x_0)_{\text{right}}$ and $d/dx W(x_0)_{\text{left}} = d/dx W(x_0)_{\text{right}}$. This allows one to solve a problem such as one dimensional reflection-refraction. We note that even though a single photon has a probability to either reflect or refract, it is a time average which shows what

is really happening and this is consistent with a conserved momentum flux (i.e. pressure). Thus, even though there is one directional flow (except for the reflected ray), there is still a constant average pressure equilibrium type of scenario.

Thus, $\exp(ipx)$, a probability math function introduced to ensure conservation of momentum through $\exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ (integrated over dx) also may be used to construct momentum flows W^* $(-d/dx) W$ which do not average out and so are consistent with conservation of momentum (and constant pressure if the coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$ s are square root fluxes). This average momentum density, however, may be created by multiplying W^* by $-id/dx W$ and so if p is discontinuous at x_0 , one may find a constant pressure (p flow) by using two continuity equations, one for p and the other for x .

Reference

1. <https://www.damtp.cam.ac.uk/user/tong/aqm/aqmten.pdf> Cambridge University